

PSEUDO DUCTILITY IN A UD CFRP MATERIAL THROUGH INTERLAMINAR AND PLY WEAKENING

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ABSTRACT

The deliberate introduction of defects in unidirectional carbon fibre composites was studied as a means of producing a pseudo-ductile tensile stress-strain behaviour. Two defect cases were investigated: weakening of plies and a combination of ply and ply interface weakening. Numerical models show that pseudo ductility can be obtained in both cases. In the first case the distance between weakenings should be small. In the second case pseudo ductility can be readily obtained but the distance between ply weakenings and the length of interlaminar weakenings can significantly affect the stress-strain response after the ‘yield’ stress. Stress-strain curves measured in initial experiments exhibit similar characteristics to model predictions for the ply weakening case.

1 INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional carbon fibre composites loaded in tension are inherently brittle. When a part made of such a composite is loaded in tension there is often little or no warning of material degradation until catastrophic failure occurs. The research described in this paper is aimed at developing composites which exhibit pseudo ductility. (Here the word *pseudo* is used to indicate that the ductility has been achieved through damage development in the composite rather than the truly ductile behaviour which occurs in metals which is due to sliding of layers of atoms relative to each at dislocations. Likewise, the *pseudo ductile strain*, ϵ_d , is defined as the increase in strain, compared to the purely elastic response, at the maximum stress).

The mechanical properties and failure mechanisms of a composite depend on several factors including the moduli and strengths of the constituents, the fibre volume fraction, the fibre-matrix interface, defects and fibre orientation [1]. Modification of some of these factors can produce a marked change in behaviour. For example, Mullin and Mazzio [2] observed that coating fibres with polyurethane, designed to reduce the bond strength between fibres and matrix, could isolate fibre fracture by debonding thus preventing premature catastrophic failure. Atkins made use of polyurethane varnish (PUV) intermittent weakening of the fibre-matrix interface to improve the toughness of unidirectional boron/epoxy composites in a very low fibre volume fraction composite ($V_f = 0.2$) leading to a four-fold increase [3]. No work has been published on modifications to introduce ductility in a single material carbon fibre system but some papers have explored other strategies for introducing ductility. Of particular relevance to the research being presented here is the investigation of hybridisation by Czél and Wisnom [4], Czél et al. [5] and Jalalvand et al. [6]. The strategy relies on enclosing a material which has a low strain to failure (in their case, carbon epoxy) with plies of a material which has a higher strain to failure (see Figure 1). Several damage modes are possible depending on the configuration and the mechanical properties of the constituent plies and the interface between them. A pseudo-ductile failure response is achieved when fragmentation in the material with the low failure strain is followed by gradual delamination growth (at an essentially constant load) at the interface with the high failure strain material. After a further increase in load, complete failure results from tensile failure of the high failure

strain material as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Gradual failure in hybrid composites

The research described in this paper, aims to exploit the same mechanisms of fragmentation and delamination to produce ductile behaviour, but in this case, in a composite of a single material rather than a hybrid system. Ply weakening is used to initiate the fragmentation process and ply interface weakening is used to modify the subsequent delamination growth process.

2 FE MODELLING

Plane strain finite element models were generated of specimens of M21/T800S unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polymer with a ply thickness of 0.184 mm, a width of 12.5 mm and a length of 150 mm. The models consisted of 12 plies with a layup of $[0^\circ/0^\circ_w/0^\circ]_4$ in which the subscript w indicates that the ply is weakened. The CFRP material was assumed to behave in a linear elastic manner and 300 evenly spaced planes of possible fracture were included in the plies using cohesive elements. The interfaces between plies were also modelled using cohesive elements. The ply and ply interface weakening was introduced by reducing the properties of selected cohesive elements.

Two defect scenarios were studied; one with ply weakening only (Figure 2) and the second one with a combination of ply and interface weakening (Figure 3). The ply weakenings are arranged in a chessboard pattern. In these figures D is the distance between weakenings in a ply, W is the length of weak ply interface (which is centred at the location of each ply weakening) and S is the length of the strong (pristine) interface (where $S = D - W$).

Figure 2. Small section of model showing ply weakening scenario

Figure 3. Small section of model showing ply and ply interface weakening scenario

The cohesive element properties were modified as follows to introduce the required weakenings:

- Interlaminar weakening was achieved by setting the strength and critical energy release rate to 10% of the pristine interface values.

- Ply weakening was achieved by setting the tensile strength and critical energy release rate to 1/3 of the pristine values.

3 SELECTED RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Ply weakening

The effect of introducing ply weakening, as shown in Figure 2Figure 3, was studied first. Different types of behaviour can be achieved by varying D , the distance between ply weakenings. Figure 4 shows that smooth ductile behaviour can be obtained when D is 2 mm with a pseudo-ductile strain $\epsilon_d = 0.36\%$. When the distance D is increased to 7 mm the pseudo-ductile strain, ϵ_d , increases but there is now a significant drop in the stress-strain response. When the distance, D , between ply weakenings is increased to 10 mm, the drop in the stress strain plot becomes so large that the maximum stress, σ_{max} , occurs at a much reduced pseudo-ductile strain, ϵ_d , and the material is predicted to fail in an almost brittle manner under load control.

Figure 4: Behaviour of models with Ply Weakening

3.2 Ply and ply interface weakening

The influence of additionally including intermittent interlaminar weakenings (as indicated in Figure 3) was also investigated. The selected results of Figure 5 show that good pseudo-ductile strains are achieved for all the values of D considered in Figure 4; the drops in the stress-strain curves are much reduced when the ply interface weakening is introduced.

Figure 5: Behaviour of models with Ply and Ply Interface weakening

Figure 6 shows the influence of increasing the extent of ply interface weakening for a fixed distance D of 4 mm between ply weakenings. It can be seen that the overall behaviour is highly influenced by the amount of interlaminar weakening; changing from a smooth behaviour with hardening to behaviours showing plateaus as W , the extent of the ply interface weakening, is increased. The pseudo ductile strain, in general, improves with increasing W and in the best case, the failure strain of the modified specimen is almost the same as the pristine one. The strengths (σ_{max}) of the specimens are very similar.

Figure 6: Influence of the amount of interlaminar weakening ($D = 4.0$ mm)

Figure 7: Influence of the amount of interlaminar weakening ($D = 6.0$ mm)

The influence of W , the length of interlaminar weakening, is again studied, this time for specimens where the distance, D , between ply weakenings is 6 mm. The plots in Figure 7 show a different trend to that observed in the previous study. In this case, the pseudo ductile strain generally slightly reduces with increasing W while the strength shows no simple trend. The first three plots show several drops in the stress-strain curves that are avoided with a further increase in W . The last two plots in Figure 7 show that too much interlaminar weakening can lead to a drop in the stress-strain curve at the start of the nonlinear behaviour.

4 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Tensile test specimens with the layup $[0^\circ/0^\circ_w/0^\circ]_4$ were prepared using M21/T800S unidirectional carbon fibre prepreg with a distance D between ply weakening of 6 mm. (Tests have yet to be completed for the case of combined ply and ply interface weakening.) Twelve plies were cut to a dimension of 310 mm x 240 mm (with the 0° direction parallel to the longer dimension) and all plies were laser cut to produce a small circular hole at each corner in order to later precisely align the plies when laying up the laminate. Four of the plies were laser cut with rows of perforations to introduce the required pattern and magnitude of ply weakening. The locations of perforations at different plies were staggered to produce the required chessboard pattern when the full laminate was laid up. The cured panel was cut to a size of 250 mm x 180 mm. Four strips of $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre reinforced epoxy end tabs (50 mm wide and 1 mm thick) were adhesively bonded onto the ends of the cured panel, leaving approximately 150 mm gauge length in the specimens. The laminate was cut using a diamond saw into specimens of 15 mm width.

Each specimen was mounted into the Instron Machine using steel wedge-grip jaws. The test was carried out using a 100 kN load cell at a displacement rate of 2 mm/min until failure. The strains were measured using an Imetrum video gauge system over a 50 mm gauge length.

Figure 8 shows the results obtained during testing. The red dotted line represents the FE-prediction of the pristine behaviour for this material and the black solid line is the FE prediction of the response of the material with ply weakenings. The specimens behaved linearly until a load drop which occurred at a high load level compared to the FE prediction. It can be seen that while some of the specimens failed in a brittle or almost brittle manner (A,B, G and H), others show considerable pseudo ductile strains (I, J) and specimen F, which also shows a relatively large pseudo-ductile strain, even fails close to the failure strain of the pristine material. Drops in the stress-strain curve can be observed in all the cases where pseudo ductile behaviour is initiated. The failure mode included a large amount of longitudinal splitting of the tested samples with large prismatic pieces of debris after final failure. The model prediction for the stress-strain curve shows very similar features in the stress-strain curve to some of the test curves after the onset of pseudo ductility, but this was predicted to occur at significantly lower stresses than measured in the experiments.

Figure 8. Experimental stress-strain plots of ply weakened specimens

5 CONCLUSIONS

Modelling predicts that pseudo-ductile behaviour can be achieved by interlaminar and ply weakening and that the behaviour can be tailored by varying the location and magnitude of these weakenings. Improved failure strains and strengths can be obtained when plies containing a “chessboard pattern” of weakenings, separated by pristine plies, are combined with intermittent weakening of ply interfaces. The behaviour is predicted to change considerably when the extent of interlaminar weakening and distance between ply weakenings are varied.

Initial experiments have shown specimens containing ply weakening exhibit characteristics similar to the model predictions. Further experimental and modelling work is underway to explore this strategy for producing pseudo-ductile high performance composites.

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